

Edentulism Leading to Foreign Body Ingestion with Small Bowel and Bladder Perforation: A Case Report

Zakaria Essaidi, El Khadim M'haimed, Soufiane Brahmi ✉, Abdelhak Ettaoussi, Khadija Kamal, Abdessamad Majd, Mounir Bouali, Abdelillah El Bakouri, Khalid Elhattabi

Department of General Surgery, IBN ROCHD University Hospital of Casablanca, Casablanca, Morocco

Abstract

Introduction: Foreign body ingestion is an uncommon but recognized cause of gastrointestinal perforation. While most cases resolve without incident, complications such as enteric fistulas and organ injuries can arise in exceptional scenarios.

Case Presentation: We report the case of a 42-year-old edentulous male who presented with signs of generalized peritonitis. Clinical examination revealed abdominal rigidity, and despite a CT scan identifying a linear hyperdense object within the jejunum suggestive of a foreign body, no clear signs of perforation were seen. Urgent surgical exploration revealed a chicken bone responsible for small bowel perforation, multiple entero-enteric fistulas, and a bladder injury. The patient's edentulism and financial inability to obtain dental prostheses contributed to the accidental ingestion of the bone.

Management and Outcome: A segmental resection of 1.8 meters of small bowel was performed with creation of a double-barrel ileostomy. The bladder breach was identified intraoperatively using a Betadine test and repaired in two layers with Vicryl 3/0. The patient recovered well and was discharged on postoperative day five.

Conclusion: This case highlights the importance of clinical judgment over imaging, especially in emergency abdominal conditions. It also underlines the significance of addressing social determinants of health, such as edentulism and poverty, in preventing life-threatening complications. Multidisciplinary collaboration, timely surgical intervention, and intraoperative vigilance were pivotal to the favorable outcome.

Introduction

Foreign body ingestion is a recognized, although rare, cause of gastrointestinal perforation [1], with potential to lead to severe complications such as enteric fistulas and organ injury. In particular, small bowel perforation and bladder injury resulting from unintentional foreign body ingestion represent complex clinical challenges [2]. This case report details the presentation, diagnosis, and management of a 42-year-old male patient who, due to edentulism and financial constraints preventing the use of dental prosthetics, accidentally ingested a chicken bone. The foreign body led to small bowel perforation, multiple enteric fistulas, and bladder injury, all of which were identified and managed through timely surgical intervention. This case underscores the critical importance of clinical

examination, intraoperative exploration, and the multidisciplinary approach required to address such multifaceted abdominal pathologies.

Presentation of the Case

We present the case of a 42-year-old male patient, a chronic smoker, who was admitted to Ibn Rochd University Hospital of Casablanca. He presented to the emergency room with diffuse abdominal pain ongoing for 15 days, associated with vomiting and fever. On examination, the patient exhibited abdominal rigidity, resembling a board-like abdomen. Additionally, he had poor oral hygiene, severe periodontitis, and near-complete edentulism.

CT scan identified a spontaneously hyperdense, linear, well-defined endoluminal material measuring approximately 4 cm within a jejunal loop, suggestive of

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Edentulism complications, Foreign body ingestion, Small bowel perforation, Bladder injury, Clinical decision-making.

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a foreign body, with associated mild diffuse fat stranding. No intra-peritoneal effusion, collection, or pneumoperitoneum was detected (figure 1).

Figure 1: Spontaneously Hyperdense Material within a Jejunal Loop Suggestive of a Foreign Body

Emergency surgery was carried out. Upon exploration, a chicken bone was found to be responsible for the patient's condition (figure 2), a cluster of small bowel loops was found, located 1.3 meters from the duodenojejunal flexure and 50 cm from the ileocecal junction, adherent to the sigmoid colon and the bladder. After dissection, the cluster was found to contain multiple entero-enteric fistulas and purulent collections (figure3).

Figure 2: A Chicken Bone Responsible for the Small Bowels and Bladder Perforations

Bladder and sigmoid integrity were assessed intraoperatively by instilling saline mixed with Povidone-Iodine. The bladder test revealed a breach on its superior surface with leakage of the solution, while the sigmoid test showed no extravasation, ruling out perforation.

Figure 3: A Cluster of Polyfistulized Small Bowel Loops

The bladder breach was subsequently repaired using a two-layer closure technique. The inner mucosal layer was approximated with Vicryl 3/0, followed by the closure of the outer serosal layer with the same suture material. The repair was tension-free, and hemostasis was achieved. An intraoperative bladder integrity test was repeated, confirming the adequacy of the repair.

A segmental resection of the small bowel was performed, excising a cluster of polyfistulized small bowel loops measuring 1.8 meters in length, located 1.3 meters from the duodenojejunal flexure and 50 cm from the ileocecal junction. A double-barrel ileostomy was then created as part of the surgical management. Peritoneal lavage was performed to cleanse the peritoneal cavity. Additionally, drainage of the pouch of Douglas was achieved using a Salem sump tube to prevent fluid accumulation and facilitate recovery. The vesical Foley catheter was retained postoperatively for continuous bladder surveillance.

During the hospitalization, diuresis was preserved, the urine was clear, and no hematuria was noted. The Foley catheter was retained for continuous monitoring and was removed once the patient showed no signs of complications. The stoma was functional by postoperative day 2. The patient was discharged home on postoperative day 5 in stable condition with instructions for follow-up care.

Discussion

This case presents a rare and complex scenario of foreign body ingestion resulting in small bowel perforation, multiple enteric fistulas, and bladder injury. The patient, a 42-year-old male with near-complete edentulism, presented with a 15-day history of diffuse abdominal pain, vomiting, and fever—clinical signs that strongly suggested peritonitis. Clinical examination plays a central role in guiding the decision for surgical exploration.

Although a CT scan identified a spontaneously hyperdense, linear endoluminal object within the jejunum—suggestive of a foreign body—it did not show definitive signs of bowel perforation. CT is highly sensitive (86%) for locating intestinal perforations in acute abdomen, aiding surgical planning. It also effectively detects small calcified foreign bodies like chicken or fish bones [1]. The absence of conclusive imaging findings did not delay the decision to operate, as clinical presentation remained the primary driver. Abdominal rigidity is a hallmark sign of generalized peritonitis, and this strong clinical indicator alone was sufficient to warrant urgent surgical exploration, even in the absence of overt radiologic findings.

Despite his edentulism, the patient had refused liquid alimentation, and financial constraints prevented the use of prosthetic dental devices to restore proper mastication. As a result, he unintentionally ingested a chicken bone. While foreign body ingestion is a recognized—though rare—cause of gastrointestinal perforation among rapid eaters [3], this case highlights how edentulism and combined with socio-economic barriers can directly lead to serious complications. In adults, diminished palatal sensation from denture wear represents the most significant risk for accidental foreign body ingestion [3]. Intraoperative exploration confirmed the chicken bone as the source of both the perforation and the resulting fistula formation. While the majority (approximately 80%) of ingested foreign bodies pass spontaneously through the digestive system without adverse effects, a significant minority (around 20%) may develop complications including obstruction, perforation, or bleeding that require clinical management [4]. This highlights the need for addressing financial and social factors in patient care, particularly when these contribute to serious health outcomes.

Surgical intervention is required in fewer than 1% of foreign body ingestion cases, with absolute indications limited to confirmed perforation. Relative indications include persistent endoscopic failure and non-resolvable complications [5]. While laparotomy remains the most common approach, laparoscopic management is appropriate for treating open intestinal perforations [6].

Bladder injuries can be difficult to detect and, in this case, were only revealed through intraoperative integrity testing [7]. The use of Povidone-Iodine mixed with saline—chosen due to the unavailability of methylene blue—proved effective in identifying the breach. Early detection allowed for a timely and secure two-layer bladder repair using Vicryl 3/0, with subsequent testing confirming restoration of bladder integrity [8].

Given the septic context and extent of bowel damage, a segmental small bowel resection was performed,

removing a 1.8-meter cluster of polyfistulized loops. A double-barrel ileostomy was created due to the high risk of anastomotic leakage, as primary anastomosis was deemed unsafe in a contaminated field [9]. Peritoneal lavage was performed, and a drain was placed in the pouch of Douglas to minimize postoperative infection risk.

Successful management relied on a multidisciplinary approach, including surgical resection with stoma creation, bladder repair, and thorough postoperative monitoring. Anesthesia and resuscitation were also key to stabilizing the patient intraoperatively and perioperatively. This case highlights the critical role of clinical judgment, intraoperative assessment, and coordinated surgical-anesthetic management in addressing complex intra-abdominal pathologies.

Conclusion

This case emphasizes the importance of clinical reasoning over imaging in the management of complex abdominal pathologies. Despite inconclusive radiologic findings, timely surgical intervention guided by clinical signs was crucial for patient survival and recovery. The rare combination of foreign body ingestion, small bowel perforation, multiple fistulas, and bladder injury highlights the necessity of thorough intraoperative assessment and prompt decision-making. Additionally, this case underscores the impact of socio-economic factors, such as edentulism and limited access to dental prosthetics, in contributing to serious health complications. Multidisciplinary collaboration between surgical, anesthetic, and supportive teams was essential in ensuring a successful outcome in this challenging, septic context.

Provenance and Peer Review

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Consent

As per international standard or university standard, patient(s) written consent has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Ethical Approval

As per international standard or university standard written ethical approval has been collected and preserved by the author(s).

Conflict of Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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